

A study on the arylazo coupling reaction of bis-(acetylacetonate)ethylenediaminocopper(II) and bis-(acetylacetonate)ethylenediaminonickel(II)

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Abstract : The electrophilic substitution of aryl diazonium ion on the Cu^{II} and Ni^{II} chelates of bis-(acetylacetonate)ethylenediamine [H_2enacac] in aqueous medium have been studied. The coupling products were isolated and characterized by elemental analysis, magnetic susceptibility measurement and electronic, infrared, ^1H NMR, ESR and mass spectral studies. The parent chelates have undergone coupling at both the acetylacetonate wings of the chelated ligand without decomposition. The geometry around the metal ion of the product is square planar as in the parent chelates. However a rearrangement is found occurred in the newly introduced azo group to hydrazone group followed by the coordination of its nitrogen to metal ion leaving the acetyl group free. As a result the coordination environment around the metal ion is changed from N_2O_2 to N_4 .

Keywords : Arylazo coupling, copper(II), nickel(II).

The substitution reactions of aryl diazonium ion on metal complexes of β -diketones have been largely studied¹⁻⁴. The present study involves the coupling reactions of aryl diazonium ions derived from aniline, *p*-chloroaniline and *p*-nitroaniline on the complexes bis-(acetylacetonate) ethylenediaminocopper(II) [$\text{CuH}_2\text{enacac}$] and its Ni^{II} analogue [$\text{NiH}_2\text{enacac}$] and the characterisation of the products [$\text{Cuenacac}(\text{X})_2$] and [$\text{Nienacac}(\text{X})_2$], where X = phenylazo (PA), *p*-chlorophenylazo (PC) or *p*-nitrophenylazo (PN) by analytical and spectroscopic methods.

Results and discussion

The arylazo substituted products formed are stable, non-hygroscopic and soluble in benzene, chloroform, nitrobenzene, acetonitrile and acetone. The analytical data (Table 1) agree with the expected composition of the coupling products. The molar conductance values measured in nitrobenzene and in acetonitrile support their non-electrolyte nature. All the Ni^{II} complexes are diamagnetic, while Cu^{II} complexes show a magnetic moment value corresponding to one unpaired electron.

The IR, electronic and ESR spectral data are presented in Table 2. The change of IR absorption band frequency corresponding to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ in the parent complex to $\nu_{\text{C}=\text{O}}$ (free carbonyl), the absence of $\nu_{\text{N}=\text{N}}$ band and presence of $\nu_{\text{N}-\text{N}}$ (hydrazone) band found in the product

Fig. 1

formed on aryl coupling reaction reveal that the arylazo coupling reaction is followed by tautomerisation of azo group to hydrazone group and the replacement of coordi-

Table 1. Analytical data of arylazo substituted derivatives of [CuH₂enacac] and [NiH₂enacac]

Complex	Mol. wt.	Colour	Weight (%) : Found/(Calcd.)				μ_{eff} (B.M.)
			Metal	C	H	N	
[Cuenacac(PA) ₂]	493.5	Brown	12.80 (12.87)	58.11 (58.35)	4.98 (5.26)	17.01 (17.00)	1.80
[Cuenacac(PC) ₂]	562.5	Brown	10.98 (11.29)	51.00 (51.19)	4.18 (4.26)	11.32 (11.43)	1.79
[Cuenacac(PN) ₂]	583.5	Red brown	10.74 (10.88)	49.11 (49.35)	4.05 (4.11)	19.13 (19.19)	1.77
[Nienacac(PA) ₂]	488.7	Brown	11.82 (12.00)	58.81 (58.93)	5.21 (5.32)	17.06 (17.18)	Dia.
[Nienacac(PC) ₂]	557.7	Brown	9.86 (10.52)	51.58 (51.63)	4.32 (4.30)	14.98 (15.06)	Dia.
[Nienacac(PN) ₂]	578.7	Dark brown	10.00 (10.14)	49.81 (49.76)	4.09 (4.14)	19.32 (19.35)	Dia.

PA = Phenylazo, PC = *p*-chlorophenylazo, PN = *p*-nitrophenylazo.

Table 2. IR, UV-Vis and ESR spectral data of the copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes

Complex	IR (cm ⁻¹)		Electronic λ_{max} (nm)	ESR ^a					
	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$	$\nu_{\text{N-N}}$		g_{\parallel}	g_{\perp}	g_{av}	A_{\parallel}	α^2_{Cu}	G
[Cuenacac(PA) ₂]	1640	1080	340 (<i>n</i> - π^*), 630 (<i>d</i> - <i>d</i>)	2.15	2.05	2.08	175.60	0.70	3.08
[Cuenacac(PC) ₂]	1640	1090	350 (<i>n</i> - π^*), 640 (<i>d</i> - <i>d</i>)	-	-	-	-	-	-
[Cuenacac(PN) ₂]	1650	1090	340 (<i>n</i> - π^*), 650 (<i>d</i> - <i>d</i>)	-	-	-	-	-	-
[Nienacac(PA) ₂]	1650	1080	350 (<i>n</i> - π^*), 470 (<i>b</i> _{2g} - <i>b</i> _{1g})	-	-	-	-	-	-
[Nienacac(PC) ₂]	1650	1080	350 (<i>n</i> - π^*), 480 (<i>b</i> _{2g} - <i>b</i> _{1g})	-	-	-	-	-	-
[Nienacac(PN) ₂]	1640	1080	340 (<i>n</i> - π^*), 490 (<i>b</i> _{2g} - <i>b</i> _{1g})	-	-	-	-	-	-

^aSpectrum recorded in CHCl₃ at liquid nitrogen temperature.

nated C-O group to free acetyl group by hydrazone group^{5,6}. Thus the N₂O₂ chromophore prevailed in the parent complex is changed to N₄ in the coupling product as reported earlier^{1,2}. The scheme of the reaction is given in Fig. 1. The electronic spectral data suggest that all the present copper(II) and nickel(II) complexes are square planar^{7,8}.

The X-band ESR spectral data of the complex, [Cuenacac(PA)₂] recorded in the frozen chloroform solution at liquid nitrogen temperature shows a parallel component with hyperfine split and unsplit perpendicular component corresponding to Cu^{II} with axial symmetry. The

values of g_{\parallel} and α^2_{Cu} suggest large amount of covalent character in the metal-ligand interaction^{8,9}. The G value suggests that the ligand is a strong field one. The $g_{\parallel} / A_{\parallel}$ of [Cuenacac(PA)₂] is 122 cm corresponding to square planar geometry. The trend $g_{\parallel} > g_{\perp} > g_{\text{el}}$ supports a square planar geometry for the complex with the unpaired electron in the $d_{x^2-y^2}$ orbital¹⁰⁻¹².

The ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) signals of [NiH₂enacac] δ 1.37 (6H, s), 1.38 (6H, s), 2.59 (4H, s) and 4.41 (2H, s) can be assigned to the protons of CH₃-C=N, CH₃-C-O, -CH₂-CH₂- and the (=CH-) groups respectively^{2,13}. In the spectra of the coupling products, [Nienacac(X)₂]

Fig. 2. The FAB mass spectrum of [Nienacac(PA)₂].

Scheme 1

(where X = PA, PC and PN), the absence of signal corresponding to =CH- and the appearance of new multi-

plet signal [δ (6.9–7.5)] of phenyl protons support the replacement of active hydrogens by arylazo group². The down field shift of the CH₃-proton signals of CH₃-CO group [δ 2.5 (6H, s)] in the coupling products substantiate the transformation of coordinated C–O group into free acetyl group.

The FAB mass spectrum of [Nienacac(PA)₂] (mol mass = 488) exhibits the base peak with m/z = 154 (Fig. 2). The peaks at m/z = 488 and 489 can be assigned to molecular ion [Nienacac(PA)₂]⁺ and (M+1) peaks respectively. The fragmentation of the complex seems to occur in two different ways as given in Scheme 1 and Scheme 2.

On the basis of the above discussion, it can be concluded that the arylazo substituted derivatives of bis-(acetylaceton)ethylenediaminocopper(II) and its Ni^{II} analogue retain the square planar geometry of their parent chelates. However the coupling reaction on [CuH₂enacac] and [NiH₂enacac] have lead to the rearrangement of coordination mode from N₂O₂ to N₄ via the tautomerisation of azo form to hydrazone form.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of analytical grade. [H₄enacac], [CuH₂enacac] and [NiH₂enacac] were prepared by the reported method¹⁴.

The arylazo substituted derivatives were prepared by the following method. 1.4 g (5 mmol) of [CuH₂enacac] or [NiH₂enacac] was dissolved in 200 mL 75% ethanol, added 8 g sodium acetate, cooled the mixture to 0° C and coupled with diazotised aniline, *p*-chloroaniline or *p*-nitroaniline (10 mmol). The products obtained were suction filtered and dried over anhydrous CaCl₂, recrystallised

Scheme 2

from acetone and checked the purity by TLC.

All the complexes were analysed for the metal content by standard procedure. C, H, N contents were estimated microanalytically. Molecular weights of the complexes were determined by Beckmann method using benzene as solvent. Molar conductance was measured in nitrobenzene and acetonitrile (10^{-3} M) on a Systronics direct reading conductivity meter. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out on a Gouy balance at room tem-

perature using $\text{Hg}[\text{Co}(\text{NCS})_4]$ as calibrant. Electronic spectra were recorded in their chloroform solution using a Shimadzu model UV-160A spectrophotometer. IR spectra were recorded in the $4000\text{--}400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region on a Bruker IFS 66V FT-IR spectrometer by KBr disc method. The ^1H NMR spectra of the Ni^{II} complexes were recorded in their CDCl_3 solution on a JEOL GSX 400 NB FT NMR spectrometer using TMS as internal standard. The X-band ESR spectrum of a Cu^{II} complex was recorded in chloroform solution at liquid nitrogen temperature using DPPH as calibrant on a Varian E-112 ESR spectrometer. The mass spectrum of Ni^{II} complex was recorded under FAB positive mode in its acetone solution on a Autospec Mass spectrometer.

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